

berilishi maqsadga muvofiq chunki o'quvchilarga ularning xatolari qayerda ekanligini aniq ko'rsatib, ularga erishish uchun kutilgan maqsadlar bilan taqqoslash imkonini beradi.

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PECULIARITIES OF THE CHRISTMAS STORY GENRE IN RACHEL JOYCE'S CREATIVITY

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Annotation: This article explores the evolution of the genre of the Christmas story using the example of Rachel Joyce's collection of short stories "A Snow Garden and other stories", which is compared with the classic Dickens' sample "A Christmas Carol".

Key words: Christmas, carnival, hero, story, genre, creative.

The tradition of the Christmas story comes from medieval mysteries, the theme and style of which was dictated by a carnival religious performance. The traditional Christmas story has a cheerful, happy ending, in which good always wins over evil. The heroes of the work find themselves in a state of spiritual or material crisis, for the resolution of which a miracle is necessary. The miracle is carried out here not only as a supernatural intervention, but also as a happy accident, a lucky coincidence. Often the structure of a calendar story includes an element of fiction, but over time it has become more oriented towards reality and now social themes occupy an important place in it.

The genre gained particular popularity in the second half of the XIX century. The founder of the genre of the Christmas story is Charles Dickens, and his most famous Christmas story is "A Christmas Carol in prose". It was Dickens who connected the Christmas and social themes, set the main postulates of the "Christmas philosophy": the value of the human soul, the theme of memory and oblivion, love for "a man in sin", the theme of childhood.

The main elements of the Christmas story:

- Timed to Christmas (the action takes place on the eve of the holiday).
- The main character is a man in a difficult situation, faced with the indifference and indifference of others.
- The hero goes through difficulties, which are overcome either by the intervention of higher forces, or by the sudden help of merciful people.
- Moral Christian issues (charity, compassion)
- Happy ending [2]

"A Christmas Carol in Prose" tells the story of an old miser Ebenezer Scrooge, who loves no one and nothing but his money. He does not see the point in celebrating Christmas, for him it is a waste of money and time. However, at home on Christmas Eve, the spirit of his late companion Jacob Marley appears in front of Scrooge, who tells him that after death he is subject to torment for not doing good

deeds during his lifetime. Marley does not want Ebenezer to suffer the same fate, and therefore, at his request, Scrooge will be visited by three Christmas spirits who will help him change for the better. So Ebenezer is visited by spirits for three nights. On the first night, the Yule spirit of the Past years comes to him, who shows him his childhood. The next night, the Spirit of the present Yuletide appears before him, he presents to him the celebration of Christmas of a variety of people, and most importantly his nephew and his clerk. On the last night, the Spirit of the future Yuletide appears, which reveals to him his possible future. After all the night trips, Scrooge decides to completely change, he sincerely enjoys Christmas, helps his loved ones, does charity work and reconciles with his nephew. And so he gains universal love and respect.

There are seven stories in Rachel Joyce's collection that are related to each other, some are directly related, being a continuation of the story, and some contain a mention of a particular character or event from a previous or subsequent story. But in all the stories there is one element, the main symbol is a poster or a photograph depicting a girl in a red raincoat.

There is no mysticism or fiction in her stories, people overcome difficulties by taking advantage of the mercy of other people, or a random coincidence decides everything. The main place is occupied by the psychological state of people, social topics.

The theme of the first story "A Faraway Smell of Lemon" is a woman's feelings about parting with a loved one. All this happens on Christmas Eve. There is a moral transformation of the character, as in the classic Christmas story, but the problem is solved not by higher powers, but by the mercy of caring people. The "magic" of the story is added by the figure of an angel, which Binnie catches sight of several times during the described day: the angel watches over her and sends her help at the most critical moment.

The following story is "The Marriage Manual". The story tells about a married couple, Alan and Alice, and their son Will, who is very worried about the difficult relationship of his parents.

The events also take place on Christmas Eve, the parents bought a bicycle for their son, and are trying to assemble it at night in the guest house, while they think their son is sleeping, but the windows of Will's room overlook the house and he watches everything that happens there.

All the problems in this story are solved by a series of accidents: the discovery of the letter, the destruction of the house, Will's surveillance. The moral of the story is that when people get married and raise children, they don't have any instructions and manuals on how to do everything right, the main thing is to love children, and so that children know about it.

"The Boxing Day Ball" is a story about young girls who go to the ball. The main character of the story is a girl named Maureen, she is modest and reserved, she always listens to her parents, but this time when the girls invited her to go to the ball with them, she could not refuse, although her mother was against it. The girl resisted the rules of her parents, and found herself in internal conflict with her conscience.

At the dance, Maureen does not dance, but only watches her friends, she notices there a young man who is not like the others, he dances alone, as if to his own music, which sounds in his head. He looks so free, and Maureen doesn't take her eyes off him for the rest of the evening. He notices that she is looking at him and decides to approach, a conversation ensues between them. A chance and at the same time fateful meeting changes their lives. They don't know what awaits them next, but they are sure that this is love at first sight. This meeting became a little Christmas miracle for them.

The title story of the collection "A Snow Garden" tells about a man who is divorced and he is going to spend the Christmas holidays with his sons. Henry was depressed for a while and hadn't seen them for a long time, and their relationship broke down. When they called him, he promised that it would snow, although the weather forecast said otherwise. Henry was terribly worried that he would not be able to fulfill his promise and disappoint his children. One day he woke up early in the morning and went to the park and saw a snow garden there, he was glad, but

when he came there the next day he did not find it and thought that he was hallucinating again. He decided to tell Owen about the garden while he was sleeping, but in fact he and Conor heard everything, and the next day they wanted to go with him, but he couldn't take them with him because he didn't exist. The children insisted, and when they came to the park, they really saw a snow garden, it was just a set for filming, and the woman invited them to enter there. The children were immensely happy about the snow, although not real, and the father was able to fulfill his promise. Their relationship improved, and they finally started calling him Dad again, and not by name.

For them, that Christmas was really magical, for them it was a Christmas miracle, despite the fact that their problems were solved by simple decorations, a coincidence. The Christmas miracle has a technogenic nature here.

So, in comparison with Dickens' "A Christmas Carol ", these stories show the everyday, social side of life, they are devoid of any mysticism. The change in the tradition of the Christmas story was strongly influenced by modernism and the modern way of life [1]. At the end of the 19th – beginning of the 20th century, there is a break with the previous artistic tradition, art, man and the world as a whole are being updated, everyone is striving for something new. People are starting to turn less to religion and believe in supernatural forces, science attracts everyone's attention. However, Rachel Joyce's stories still retain the basic elements of the Christmas story as a genre. The main element is that the stories are timed for Christmas. The main characters of the stories are people who have fallen into a difficult situation, faced difficulties or simply got confused in their lives; the heroes overcome difficulties by turning to other people for help or advice, or the solution is by itself, a random combination of circumstances, unlike Dickens, where higher powers, the Spirits of Christmas, come to the hero's aid. There is also a moral Christian theme in the stories, perhaps, although it is not expressed as vividly and clearly as in Dickens. And, of course, a happy ending, perhaps in these stories it is not always happy, but it always ends with a solution to the problem and implies a happy future. And most importantly, the stories retained such an element

as morality and edification, without this element, these stories would not have made sense and the power with which they touch the soul.

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DIFFICULTIES OF POETIC TRANSLATION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article gives peculiarities of poetic translation in Uzbek and English languages with examples in turn. As these two languages belong to different language families, translators may face various difficulties while they are translating literary poets. Rhymed words, inversion and other stylistic devices are main essences of poetry so translators must follow the rhythm, musical-literary tune in poems. Although poetic translation seems more complicated than prosaic translation, it is one of the developing fields in translation.